

Poem

Daily Paris

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Introduction by the Author

"Daily Paris" is Pilar Osorio's first English published poem; it was written in a poetry class with Martín Espada. The poem explores alienation and frustration in the middle of relationship's crisis; it begins with an idyllic scene, but the tone shifts dramatically when the speaker wakes up in noisy Paris, resenting their partner snoring next to them. The Paris portrayed in the poem, far from the cliché, becomes overwhelming and suffocates the speaker. In the city of light, the speaker is unable to communicate; she is always stuck in her "Mierda" (meaning "shit" in Spanish). The poem delves into the speaker's reflections and judgments. They consider themselves a judge, observing and critiquing various aspects of French society, their own prejudices, and their Colombian roots. The poem is a reality check on love and Paris and aims to be radically honest on the speaker's sense of self, fears, anger and vulnerability. The poem evokes literary references, mentioning la Maga (a character from Julio Cortázar's novel "Hopscotch"), living a season in hell (referring to Arthur Rimbaud's work), and the spleen (a motif in Charles Baudelaire's poetry).

Daily Paris

- Pilar Osorio Lora

The grass in my back,
The sound of water jumping into the soil,
Tabaré barking.
My sister's silhouette walking back from school,
Mom watering the plants,
Tabaré running into my sister,
Mom smiles.

I wake up in a noisy Paris
Hating the one who snores by my side
He snores without rhythm
No one has rhythm in Paris
It's only light and smoke
His voice is just noise
Noise overlapping noise
His snoring
His breathing
His walking
His arms
He

Noise

I walk out of the building
I ask for a coffee with my hands
I can't speak this fucking Parisian French
I can't ask for a coffee and not be stared at
I pretend I don't know what I do know

I light a cigarette
I want to write a love poem
But I can't, I just write the first word
-Mierda-
Never had shit been so cleansing
Words come like a river, a cascade
They rule my body
They vomit this obligated silence

Free advice: don't marry a smart guy
Asking for forgiveness dries up your words

I listen to my breathing
My lungs whistle
They always have
I stare at my "Mierda"
Inhale
Exhale

I see Belleville
The half bike appearing from a wall in Oberkampf's corner
The green Mc Donald's full, always full
The non-stop coffee
The immigrants
They
Me
We are all immigrants here

But I am more
I am a monster
I am a judge
Of non-addressed French racism
Of colorless people
My own racism
Of *interdit* and *pardon*
Of Colombian permissiveness
My useless patriotism
Of my homophobia
Of my clichés

I am a judge
Of Cortázar's, Baudelaire's and Rimbaud's euphemisms
I judge the bad taste of French coffee
I judge Colombian pretensions at being coffee experts
The skinny men
The over-made-up women
I judge me
These small breasts
My washed-up face
I judge myself
This cowardice
This melancholy

But -shit- I have no money, no family, no friends, no job, I only have his noise and this Mac.

Free advice: don't leave everything you love for someone you love
Re-read
It is not advice
It is common sense
Shit
Mierda
Merde

I am a brainless judge
My courtroom is a café
My gavel a Mac
My audience a cigarette
My law a cliché
My jury Hollywood actors
My supervisors my friends

I finish the coffee
I won't sleep after it
I read the poem
I won't forget

I half-smile,
I am what I wanted to be
I am la Maga
I am living a season in hell
I am the spleen
Mierda
I never learned to read

Stop. Think:
my sister,
Tabaré,

the grass,
the water,
Mom's smile.
I beat
I breathe
I remember

The apartment's light is on
Snore are over
It's yelling time
Free advice: Write. Some nights, snore on purpose.

Glossary

Tabaré	-	Male Dog
Silhouette	-	An image / shadow of a person
Mierda	-	'Shit' in Spanish
Merde	-	A humorous way of telling shit
Oberkampf's Corner	-	A Place in Paris, France.
Mc Donald's	-	A Restaurant
<i>Interdit</i>	-	Forbidden
Homophobia	-	dislike or prejudice against gay people
Cortázar	-	Julio Florencio Cortázar was an Argentine and a nationalized French writer. He is known as one of the founders of the Latin American Boom. He influenced an entire generation of Spanish-speaking readers and writers in America and Europe with his writing.
Baudelaire	-	Charles Pierre Baudelaire was a famous French poet, essayist, art critic and translator. His poems are known for its mastery of rhyme and rhythm having a pulse inherited from Romantics. Most of them are based on his observations on real life.
Rimbaud	-	Jean Nicolas Arthur Rimbaud was a famous French poet known for his transgressive and surrealistic themes in his writings and for his influence on modern French literature and arts.
la Maga	-	A character from Julio Cortázar's novel "Hopscotch"

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